

Deliverable Overview

No.	Description	Location
1.1	Deliverable template: A deliverable template is available that serves as template for all other deliverables. This template should secure that all deliverables can be easily aggregated to a final report.	<u>Deliverable Collection</u> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15836578 → <i>D1-1_LEAP-RE_Template.pdf</i> → <i>D1-1_LEAP-RE_OASES-Template.pdf</i>
1.2	Final report: All deliverables will be aggregated to a final report with supplementary sections describing the overall project success, summary and connectivity.	<u>Zenodo & Deliverable Collection</u> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16258385 → <i>D1-2_OASES_Final-Report.pdf</i>
2.1	EO-Codes for RES detection: pre-trained model for the spatial detection of PV and wind power sites in open-source earth observation data with documentation and application examples are available and described.	<u>GitHub, Zenodo & Publications</u> https://github.com/Kleebaue/multi-resolution-pv-system-segmentation https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10036926 https://www.mdpi.com/2072-4292/15/24/5687 https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10641018
2.2	EO based RES data base: Site information for PV and wind turbines for South Africa, Algeria and Egypt are available as open-source data.	<u>Zenodo & Publications</u> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15294535 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15221465 https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi14060232
3.1	Report on current available datasets on wind and solar as well as software, methodologies and techniques for wind power and PV time series generation.	<u>Deliverable Collection & Zenodo</u> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15372696 → <i>D3-1_OASES_Literature-Data-Study-Report.pdf</i>

3.2	Description of the general model for wind power and PV time series generation for any future scenario.	<p>Publication, Zenodo & Deliverable Collection https://www.mdpi.com/2673-9941/5/1/8 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15372631</p> <p>→ <i>D3-2_OASES_Model-Description.pdf</i></p>
3.3	<p>Potential analyses for RES in Algeria, Egypt & South Africa.</p> <p><i>* Updated for alignment with the project structure.</i></p>	<p>Deliverable Collection https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15836578</p> <p>→ <i>D3-3_OASES_Potential-Analyses.zip</i></p>
4.1	Repository for the workflows.	<p>GitHub & Zenodo https://github.com/irena-flextool/flextool</p> <p>→ <i>D5-2_OASES_Case-Study-Report.pdf</i></p>
4.2	Documentation of new features in IRENA FlexTool.	<p>GitHub Documentation https://irena-flextool.github.io/flextool/</p>
4.3	Conversion tools to convert input data from OASES workflow to two others energy system models.	<p>GitHub https://github.com/ines-tools/ines-flextool https://github.com/ines-tools/ines-pypsa</p>
5.1	Open source and data: Report with detailed information about the available OASES source code, data and model chain.	<p>Deliverable Collection & Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13365309</p> <p>→ <i>D5-1_OASES_Open-Source-and-Data-Strategy-Report.pdf</i></p>
5.2	Case study report: Report describing the calculation and results of the national case studies from Egypt, Algeria and South Africa.	<p>Deliverable Collection & Zenodo https://zenodo.org/records/13304369 https://zenodo.org/records/15222894 https://zenodo.org/records/15275481 https://zenodo.org/records/14843471 https://zenodo.org/records/13318686 https://zenodo.org/records/15341304</p> <p>→ <i>D5-2_OASES_Case-Study-Report.pdf</i></p>
5.3	<p>Comprehensive Dissemination & Communication Strategy.</p> <p><i>* Adjusted due to partner withdrawal and for coherence.</i></p>	<p>Deliverable Collection https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15836578</p> <p>→ <i>D5-3_OASES_Dissemination-and-Communication-Plan.pdf</i></p>

